

THE USE OF A SMALL PULTRUDER FOR SPECIMEN PREPARATION

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SUMMARY: One of the difficulties in studying composite materials lies in the preparation of uniform specimens easily and quickly. It must be possible to change various characteristics of materials and the cure cycle with a minimum of "fuss". It must also be possible to test such specimens without a quantity of specialized equipment so that a small production facility can have the quality control and flexibility for quality monitoring that is characteristic of larger production units. This paper will describe a small pultruder which is compact and versatile enough to produce such specimens and also some apparatus that will test the debonding energy of the resin-fiber bond which property is, perhaps, the key item in developing reliable properties of the composite itself.

KEYWORDS: pultruder, benchtop, debonding energy in shear, property determination

INTRODUCTION

The process of pultrusion is deceptively simple: an impregnated strand is pulled through a heated die. It cures and the hard rod is pulled to a cutoff and simply severed into the correct lengths. The problems that need to be addressed include the following:

1. What is the optimum material?
2. What are its curing characteristics?
3. What is optimum pultrusion speed?
4. What kind of properties can we expect?
5. Is it possible to readily change the materials without incurring an unreasonable cost?
6. Can I use simple apparatus to determine various properties?

We have developed a small benchtop pultruder (1) to address each of these problems and believe that it is a useful production tool as well as being a splendid research apparatus.

DESCRIPTION OF APPARATUS

The benchtop pultruder consists of the following items:

1. A small temperature controlled hotplate to determine the gel times of resins at different temperatures.
2. An impregnation bath which uses disposable plastic cups.
3. A controllable speed puller.

4. A stainless steel die with two heat zones: the first zone is 0.11 m long, the second zone is 0.18 m long and each has a separate temperature controller.
5. The pultruder produces a specimen 3 mm diameter. This is large enough to show the properties of a larger section and small enough to require a minimal creel. It is also small enough to permit manual cutting so that expensive saws are not needed.
6. The overall dimensions are 1.6 m long, 0.6 m wide and 0.4 m high. The spools of fiber will sit on the floor under the bench that is supporting the pultruder so a minimal floor space is needed.
7. The die is removable so that it can be slid out of the heating elements and simply be burned out if it should jamb. It can then be rethreaded and restarted with a minimum of "fuss".
8. The fibers can be lifted out of the resin bath and run to dryness so that it can easily and cleanly be restarted after being stopped.

What we have tried to produce is equipment that is eminently simple for any experimental use. Fig. 1.

USING THE SYSTEM

There are three key items to be measured before it is possible to scale up the sections sizes:

1. The gel-time plot for various temperatures.
2. The fracture energy is shear for various combinations of materials and time-temperature relationships.
3. The shear modulus in torsion of the pultruded rod.

The temperature-time relationship for gelling and curing is determined by using the small temperature controlled hotplate. Drip some of the resin on it. Stir the resin to gel and note the time of gelling demanded at the temperatures you might expect. A typical plot is shown in Fig. 2.

This curve is the key item for determining the speed and temperature of the die.

The curve in Fig. 2 is for a typical resin system (Owens-Corning E-606 polyester resin with 1% benzoyl peroxide and 1% SP-48 Specialty Products release agent) the curve shows a sharp decrease in time as the temperature is increased. The inflection in the curve occurs here at about 150°C. This we shall refer to as the Critical Cure Temperature T_c . It will control the speed of pulling and temperature of the die. It is essential that both the surface and interior of the pultrusion reaches this temperature.

We found (2) that raising the temperature of cure to more than 25°C above T_c is deleterious as the resin becomes more waxy than if cured at T_c . This can be avoided by raising the surface temperature to about 10°C below T_c . This allows the exotherm to bring the interior up to T_c .

The time needed to reach T_c is about 7 s so, with a 0.3 m die we can expect to need a pultrusion speed of about $0.3/7 = 0.04$ m/s. It should be recognized that the resin will shrink in the die. This will tend to pull the product away from the die so it will be practical to use a slightly lower pulling speed than directly calculated - or we can use a postcure oven when the product can be exposed to radiant heat, again at a controlled temperature. The ovens supplied

with the system are 0.3 m long so we can essentially double the pulling speed when we use an oven.

QUALITY CHECKING

The checking of the quality of a pultruded product is central to optimizing the pultrusion variables. The optimum way of doing this is by a measurement of the fracture energy in shear of a rod.

This parameter is exactly what we seek - a measure of the bonding of fibers to resin. The problem with doing just this is that the measurement of such properties is somewhat awkward and described in reference (1). What we also notice from (2) is that the fracture energy in shear closely parallels the shear modulus in torsion.

This is a much simpler quantity to measure and can easily be done using a small torsion tester - this can be commercial Fig. 4 or it can be made from a simple construction kit (3).

The results of such a test are shown in Fig. 3

Essentially, what we see from this test is that there is definitely an optimum dwell time in the die. This translates to an optimum speed of draw and can be determined easily and experimentally for any material combination. It also shows that there is a sharp drop-off in properties if we wander from this optimum value.

SCALE-UP TO LARGER SECTIONS

The experimental work has been done on 3 mm rod which is often not a useful pultrusion site. It is incumbent to be able to decide speeds and temperatures on a larger section. This can be done by making the assumption that the diffusivity of the specimen is a constant and about $7 \times 10^{-8} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$ (2). Then we can calculate the time required for the center temperature to be within 10°C of the outer surface.

This is done by approximating from simple heat transfer formulae (4).

The results are that values of T_c are related by the inverse square of the diameter of the rod. So an easy scale up is possible after we have determined the T_c for the 3 mm rod.

These values of T_c will depend on many factors and must be computed on the basis of approximation when sections of unusual shape are being made. It is often desirable that a post curing oven be used to ensure complete cure and to obviate the necessity for an impractically long die.

CONCLUSIONS

The usefulness of a small pultruder lies in its ability to determine some vital parameters of the process:

1. The optimum die temperatures
2. The optimum die dwell time
3. The optimum material for your purpose
4. The expected material properties.

And this all being done in a small space and with a minimum expenditure of material and time.

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Figure 1: Bench Pultruder

Figure 2: The time required for a resin system to gel when in contact with surfaces at various temperatures

Figure 3: The shear modulus of the pultruded rod plotted against various dwell times in the die, for different die inlet temperatures, showing an optimum dwell time and die temperature exists

Figure 4: Mechanical torsion tester